

SUBJECT: ANEMIA AND ITS TYPES.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7791305>

Abstract: This article aims to make nurses working in treatment and prevention institutions and family polyclinics more mature in all respects, to have sufficient knowledge, qualifications, skills in specialized disciplines, to further improve medical assistance in self-management and counseling, aimed at strengthening new theoretical knowledge through practical skills, mastering psychological care skills.

Key words: Anemia, iron deficiency, nurse, hemoglobin, medicine, leukocytes, erythrocytes, platelets, vessel, plasma, blood.

Enter.

The concept of blood system was described by GFLang in 1939.

In this system he introduced the following:

- 1) Peripheral blood circulating in the veins;
- 2) Blood forming organs;
- 3) Organs where blood is consumed;
- 4) Controlling neuro-humoral apparatus.

Blood, lymph and tissue fluid form the internal environment of the body, washing all the cells and tissues in the body. The composition of the internal environment and the relative constancy of its physico-chemical properties differ. Due to this, a relatively constant condition (homeostasis) is created for the survival of body cells. The blood plays a very important role in maintaining the stability of these conditions, that is, homeostasis. This system includes the liver, bone marrow, lymph nodes, and the spleen. Here are blood-forming elements: erythrocytes are produced mainly in the red bone marrow, leukocytes - in the spleen and lymph nodes (monocytes are one form of leukocytes in the spleen, and lymphocytes are produced in the lymph nodes), platelets - in the red bone marrow. Blood delivers nutrients to all cells of the body and removes harmful products.

Blood plasma is water, in which protein substances, sugar, very small fat particles, various salts, acid rod (in small amount) are dissolved.

It contains up to 5×10^{12} /l erythrocytes. They give the blood a red color because they hold a specific hemoglobin substance. The erythrocytes passing through the lungs with blood, due to their unique structure (in particular, iron is included in the hemoglobin), take oxygen and transport it to all organs and tissues.

The lifespan of erythrocytes is about one month, they are broken down more in the spleen (less often in the liver, bone marrow), so the spleen is called the "grave" of erythrocytes.

Hemoglobin released after erythrocyte destruction is a component of bilirubin, which forms iron, iron is used for the "vision" of new erythrocytes.

Leukocytes are able to move (amoeba type of movement), they can digest substances foreign to the body, for example, dead cells (phagocytosis). Unlike erythrocytes, leukocytes retain a

cell nucleus. There are leukocytes in the blood in the norm - from $3.2 \times 10^9 / l$ to $11.3 \times 10^9 / l$. Granulocyte (with granular protoplasm) and agranulocyte (non- granular) leukocytes are distinguished. Granulocytes are divided into acidophilic granulocytes (eosinophils), basophilic, neutrophilic granulocytes. Agranulocytes are lymphocytes and monocytes. in relation to the total number of leukocytes, granulocytes make up about 60-65%, lymphocytes - 19-37%, monocytes - up to 3-11%, acidophilic granulocytes - 2%, basophilic granulocytes - 0-1.0%. - Thrombocytes participate in blood clotting. Normally, their amount is from $180.0 \times 10^9 / l$ to $320.0 \times 10^9 / l$ or 50 platelets per 1000 erythrocytes.

Functions of blood.

Moving in the blood vessels, it performs the following functions in the body:

1. Transport task. Blood transports various substances from one point of the body to another and thus performs the function of transportation.
2. Breath function. As the blood passes through the capillaries of the small circulatory circle, it binds to O_2 and delivers it to the tissues. While passing through the arteries, it gives O_2 and attaches SO_2 to itself.
3. The function of trophic nutrition or blood supplies all cells with necessary nutrients (glucose, amino acids, fats, vitamins, mineral salts and water).
4. Excretory function. The waste products of metabolism - diuretics, uric acid, etc. are carried away from blood vessels and they are removed from the body through excretory organs.
5. Thermoregulatory function. As the blood flows through the organs with high heat production, it warms and transfers this heat to the organs with slow heat production. In this way, the blood is involved in maintaining the constant body temperature.
6. Homeostatic task. A number of constants of blood homeostasis (pH, osmotic pressure, etc.) are involved in maintaining the same.
7. They participate in the exchange of water and salts between blood and cells.
8. H protection duty. Red blood cells - leukocytes are involved in the process of phagocytosis. Globulins, which are white blood cells, are considered antibodies. Blood clotting is a protective function.
9. It is used in humoral head washing. Blood transports hormones and other biologically active substances and takes an active part in humoral regulation.
10. The creator implements the parts. Plasma and Macromolecules transported by q on-shaped elements are involved in the transfer of intercellular information.

Blood composition.

Blood consists of two parts: liquid part - plasma and suspended elements in it (erythrocytes, leukocytes and thrombocytes).

There is a certain volume ratio between blood plasma and shaped elements. It is called the hematocrit index. It is determined using a special glass tube divided into pieces - hematocrit. If q on is centrifuged in a hematocrit tube, q on is separated into plasma and form elements. In this case, the plasma volume is 55-60% of the blood volume, and the shaped elements are 40-45%. Shaped elements make up 44-46% of blood volume in men, and 41-43% in women.

It is the medicine of the body.

In the body of an adult, the total volume of water is 6-8% of the body weight (4-6 liters). The total amount of blood in the body is relatively constant. K o' p Blood depletion as a result of blood transfusion, for example, 1/3 (33%) of the total blood volume, can lead to the

destruction of the body . In the experiment, black dye is used to determine the total amount of blood in the body .

Blood

Formed elements of blood include erythrocytes or red blood cells, leukocytes or red blood cells, and platelets or blood platelets .

Erythrocytes or red blood cells in humans and mammals are uninucleate, homogeneous protoplasmic h cells .

In the structure of erythrocytes, there is a difference between cell support - stroma and surface layer - membrane . The erythrocyte membrane is composed of two layers of phospholipids. There is a monomolecular white coat on the inside and outside . 1 mm³ of healthy men 5-6 million at the moment . erythrocytes , and 4.5-5 million in women. there is an erythrocyte . 25 trillion in all the blood in the human body . erythrocyte b dies , it is called erythron. Erythrocytes are drug - resistant . _ _ _ An increase in them is called erythrocytosis or erythremia, and a decrease is called erythropenia or anemia.

An individual erythrocyte has a diameter of 7.2-7.5 μm, a thickness of 2.2 μm, and a volume of 90 μm³ . The total surface of all erythrocytes is 3000 m² is _ This is 1500 times more than the body surface of an adult .

unique shape of erythrocytes helps to create such a large surface . Human erythrocytes are flat- shaped and sunken in from both sides . This form of the erythrocyte is convenient for better performance of its main task, that is, the task of carrying O₂ from the respiratory organs to the cells of the body . Since the erythrocyte is a cell without a nucleus in mammals, it consumes 200 times less O₂ than its predecessors - erythroblast and normoblast . The erythrocyte membrane differs from the membrane of other cells in the body in that it is less permeable to Na⁺ and K⁺ ions · HCO₃⁻ and Cl⁻ ions , as well as O₂ , CO₂ , It passes H⁺ and OH⁻ ions well . The mineral content of erythrocyte and plasma is not the same: human erythrocytes have more potassium than sodium . In plasma, it is the opposite. Hemoglobin makes up 90% of the dry matter in the erythrocyte, and 10 % of the blood is other white matter , lipids , glucose and mineral salts .

Hemoglobin.

Hemoglobin is a complex chromoprotein with a molecular weight of 64458. It is composed of globin protein and 4 molecules of heme. A heme molecule with an iron atom can attach and donate an O₂ molecule. At the same time, the valence of iron that binds O₂ gas does not change, that is, iron has two valences. Hemoglobin's active prosthetic group is h , and globin is a heme-carrying white cell . Healthy men have 14-16 g% (140-160 g/l) and women have 12-14 g% (120-140 g/l) of hemoglobin. The total amount of hemoglobin in the body is 700 grams. K is often determined in the clinic by a quantity known as the color index . Color k ' indicator - shows the level k' of erythrocytes' interaction with hemoglobin . It can be calculated by dividing the amount of hemoglobin by the amount of erythrocytes . Normally, the color index is 0.8-1.0 . A color index above 1.0 is called hyperchromasia , and below 0.8 is called hypochromasia. Hemoglobin is synthesized by erythroblasts and normoblasts in red blood cells .

Erythrocyte sedimentation rate.

When blood with anticoagulants (anticoagulants) is added to the test tube, the erythrocytes sink. To determine the erythrocyte sedimentation rate (EChT), blood is mixed with a 5% solution of sodium citrate, taken into a millimeter glass tube and installed in a PAPanchenkov

apparatus. After one hour, the height of the clear layer above is calculated. EChT is 1-10 mm/h in men, 2-15 mm/h in women, 0.5-1.0 mm/h in newborns. EChT in pregnant women can reach 45-50 mm/hour. EChT depends on the properties of plasma, including the amount of globulins and fibrinogen in plasma. High molecular weight plasma proteins reduce the charge of shaped elements and their repulsion from each other. As a result, erythrocytes stick together and sink.

Leukocytes.

Leukocytes or white blood cells participate in the protection of the body against microbes, viruses, and various foreign substances, that is, they provide immunity. There are 4,000-9,000 leukocytes in 1 mm³ of the blood of an adult. Their increase is called leukocytosis, and their decrease is called leukopenia. Leukocytosis can be physiological or reactive. Physiological leukocytosis can occur in a healthy person as a result of eating, physical work, strong excitement, pain somewhere. It is related to the redistribution of blood in the body. Reactive leukocytosis is observed in inflammatory, allergic and tumor diseases and is characterized by a large release of immature leukocytes from blood-forming organs. All leukocytes have granules in their protoplasm. depending on their absence, they are divided into two large groups: granulocytes - granular leukocytes and agranulocytes - non-granular leukocytes.

Granulocytes are divided into the following, depending on the dyes used to stain the granules:

1. Eosinophils (grains are stained with acidic substances , for example , with eosin) ;
2. Basophils (grains are composed of basal cells) ;
3. Neutrophils (granules are stained with neutral cells).

are two types of agranulocytes :

1. Monocytes .
2. Lymphocytes .

The percentage ratio between different types of leukocytes is called leukocyte formula or leukogram. Every person's leukogram is relatively constant, and its changes are a sign of various diseases. Neutrophils are 50-75% of all leukocytes is organized . _ The main function is phagocytosis and the production of antibodies. Neutrophils can act like amoebas . Their movement speed is equal to 40 μm per minute . Each neutrophil can swallow up to 15-20 bacteria. Eosinophils are involved in breaking down and neutralizing leukocyte toxins and leukocytes . The number of eosinophils in allergic conditions (bronchial asthma, rheumatism, ringworm, etc.) Heparin and histamine are present in the granules in the protoplasm of basophils . The number of basophils increases in the final stage of acute inflammation and in chronic inflammation . Heparin in these cells promotes blood clotting , and histamine improves blood flow in microcirculatory vessels . This helps the processes of absorption and maturation in the hearths of wild growth . Blood circulating in the human body has been well studied by scientists. In recent years, radioactive indicators have been used to study blood. Blood is taken from the subject , erythrocytes are separated from the plasma and placed in a solution with radioactive phosphorus. Radioactive phosphorus is absorbed into erythrocytes. Targeted erythrocytes are injected back into the blood vessel of the person being examined , and after they are evenly distributed throughout the blood, a small amount of blood is taken for examination, and its level of radioactivity is determined. Then the total amount of blood is determined by counting . The total amount of blood in the human body is 7% of the body mass, i.e. 1/13, or 70 ml per 1 kg of weight. In newborns, blood makes up 15% of the body mass and corresponds to 93-147 ml per 1 kg of weight. Such a large volume of blood in children

compared to adults is due to a high level of metabolism. When the child reaches 12 years of age, the amount of blood in him approaches the characteristic level for adults. During puberty, the amount of blood increases slightly and corresponds to 7-78 ml per 1 kg of weight. The amount of blood circulating in the veins varies from person to person, depending on the condition and needs of the body. The amount of circulating blood increases especially when doing physical work, when excited, when the external temperature rises, when there is a lack of oxygen for a while. When adults sleep and rest, only half of their blood moves in the veins, and the other half is stored in blood depots. There are two types of blood depots: partially blocked and partially blocked. A complete stopping depot includes the spleen. Blood circulation in its venous sinuses temporarily stops, and it also thickens, and its erythrocytes almost double. Thus, the spleen is not only a blood depot, but also a erythrocyte depot.

includes the skin, liver, other organs and parts of the body. In them, the blood movement slows down dramatically, as a result of which the circulating blood is partially reduced, that is, a part of the blood participates less in the general circulation.

The blood-forming and blood-decomposing organs that move along the blood vessels together form the blood system. Organisms that make blood cells are called hematopoietic organisms.

These organisms include red marrow, liver, lymph nodes, spleen. In red marrow, erythrocytes, granular leukocytes, monocytes; Lymphocytes are formed in the lymph nodes, tonsils, and lymphocytes and monocytes are formed in the spleen. In an adult organism, the liver is deprived of the function of blood formation. The formation of a strong skeleton is accompanied by the formation of a blood-forming organism. Nature has protected this organism with bones. Even if the bones fail, the activity of the blood-forming organs is not disturbed. For example, a person gets injured and begins to lose a lot of blood. In this case, the bone marrow rapidly increases blood production.

Blood formation is influenced by internal and external factors in the body. First of all, the nervous system is seen. For example, blood-forming organs are very rich in nerves, and factors such as emotion, muscle work, temperature changes, lack of O₂ in the body significantly change the composition of blood cells.

Generally, every nurse should know about anemia and its types, regardless of their field of work, and know how to carry out preventive measures among the population. This article can provide basic knowledge and skills to the medical worker. Currently, in the field of medicine, special attention is paid to improving the level of knowledge and skills of secondary medical workers. The article presents materials aimed at adequately mastering the necessary new knowledge and skills in accordance with the qualification description and job instructions of all nurses of treatment and prevention institutions and nurses of QVP/QOP/OP and district/city KTPPs. In this regard, prevention of dangerous complications for patients, implementation of care aimed at formation of a proper lifestyle, and improvement of independently conducted training activities will be achieved. Within the scope of the topic, it is intended to train nurses of the therapy department working in DPMs, patronage/family nurses working in QVP/QOP/OP and district/city KTPPs. Nurses must be able to provide skilled medical care when necessary. Based on this, it is necessary to give advice to the population about anemia and its types, to teach them theoretical and practical aspects in every way.

Formation of blood - the phenomenon of hemopoiesis, that is, the scheme of formation of mature cells in peripheral blood was developed by Chertkov and Vorobyov in 1973. In this

case, cells grow in a certain order depending on their level of nutrition. 3 branches appear from the stem cell: the branch that produces leukocytes, erythrocytes, platelets.

In the table of blood formation, all cells are divided into 6 classes:

Class 1, 2, 3, 4 — cells up to maturity.

Class 5 — maturing cells.

Class 6 — mature cells.

1st class. The amount of stem cells is found in the total percentage of blood-forming tissues. From the stem cell, all branches of blood formation develop. A stem cell is called polypotent. Most of the stem cell is in a uniform state, of which 10% divides.

2nd class. It is a partially polypotent cell. From this, lymphopoiesis begins (cells of the lymphoid line are formed).

3rd class. Unipotent cells. They are initial formation for lymphocyte, monocyte, granulocyte, Er and Fd.

4th grade. These include young cells, myeloblast, i.e. "blast" cells. Plasmoblast, lymphoblast, monoblast, misloblast, erythroblast, megablast. During the division of these cells, the next class is formed.

5th grade. Maturing cells enter these, and their names start with "pro" and end with "sit". Elements belonging to this class are placed vertically in the scheme - one after the other, according to their progress.

6th grade. This class includes mature cells: plasmocide, lymphocyte, monocyte, segmented neutrophils. Mature cells migrate from bone marrow to peripheral blood. So, the development of blood cells - hemopoiesis takes place in the body where blood is created. According to the average unitary theory of Papengheim-Kryukov, hemopoiesis is a hemocytoblast. It is an oval, round, pale pink cell with a large nucleus. Each mature cell performs a specific function.

Blood is a liquid tissue that moves continuously in the veins; reaches cells and tissues and ensures their vital activity and physiological functions. Since it moves continuously within the veins, it mainly acts as a carrier in the body. Blood is composed of plasma and shaped elements. A certain ratio is maintained between this part of the blood. 55% of the volume of blood corresponds to plasma, the remaining 45% of the volume is made up of shaped elements. The total amount of blood in an adult's body is 6-8% of body weight, i.e. 4-6 l. Not all blood in the body moves through the blood vessels under normal conditions. A part of it is kept in reserves. 20% of the total amount of blood is in the liver, 16% in the spleen, about 10% in the skin vessels, and may not participate in the blood circulation for a certain period of time.

Depending on the nature and importance of transported substances, the following activities of blood: 1) respiration; 2) feeding; 3) excretory; 4) management; 5) providing creative controls; 6) homeostatic; 7) temperature control and 8) protection activities are differentiated.

1) Breathing activity. This activity refers to the delivery of oxygen from the lungs to the tissues and the transport of carbon dioxide produced in them to the lungs. Erythrocytes are also important in the transport of carbon dioxide.

2) Nutrition. The nutritional activity of the blood consists in the delivery of nutrients from the organs of the digestive system to the tissues. The complex polymer substances in the consumed food are broken down by enzymes in the stomach and small intestine and turn into simple monomeric substances that can be absorbed. Glucose, fructose, galactose, amino acids,

salts and other water-soluble substances are absorbed into the blood. Fats are mainly absorbed into the lymph and are poured into the blood. Carbohydrates mainly serve as a source of energy. A small part of them turns into glycogen in the liver and muscles, creating a small reserve. Cells spend most of their amino acids on protein synthesis. Neutral fats are synthesized from fatty acids in the presence of glycerol and are stored in the fat tissue. When necessary, glucose from glycogen, neutral from liver tissue is transferred to the blood and used as a source of energy.

3) Excretory activity. Excretory activity of the blood is the participation in the removal of residual substances formed as a result of metabolism, substances introduced into the body accidentally or with a specific purpose. Ensuring the elimination of excess water, ingested salt and nutrients is also part of the excretory function. Excretion of the blood supplies the necessary substances to the excretory organs.

4) Management activities. It is known that all organs and tissues in the body release physiologically active substances into the blood. As the blood transports these substances throughout the body, it controls the humors, connects the organs, unites the body, and adapts to changes in the environment.

5) Curator activity. This activity of the blood can be called a part of the management activity. This activity consists in the participation of blood plasma and shaped elements in the transport of macromolecules with information. These macromolecules affect protein synthesis, cell division, and other processes after being delivered to the appropriate location.

6) Homeostatic activity. Blood fluids maintain the stability of rN, osmotic pressure, electrolyte content, amount of organic matter and other indicators.

7) Involvement in temperature control. As a result of the activity of cells and tissues, heat is continuously transferred to large organs (liver, deep muscles, heart), it is not released directly to the external environment. The blood passing through the veins of these organs warms up to a certain degree and distributes the heat throughout the body. If the blood temperature increases significantly, the thermoreceptors in the hypothalamus are activated, and the activity of the mechanisms that control the temperature increases. As a result, skin capillaries expand, sweat secretion increases, heat loss accelerates.

8) Protection activity. Various components of the blood participate in the emergence of this activity. The protective activity consists primarily of ensuring the destruction of microbes that cause infectious diseases (cellular immunity) and the production of antibodies against these microbes and their poisons (humoral immunity). Blood clotting is also a protective reaction.

Anemias.

Anemia is the most common disease in which hemoglobin and erythrocytes are reduced. Anemia is caused by excessive blood loss (bleeding), decreased red bone marrow function, lack of substances necessary for the body's blood formation processes, in particular, cyanocobalamin or iron deficiency, as well as infectious toxic effect on bone marrow. Hypochromic and hyperchromic anemias are distinguished by blood color index.

Anemia and its types.

Current at the time clinical landscape to himself special has been of anemias a lot occurring the following types difference will be done.

1. Posthemorrhagic anemia, blood loss as a result appear will be
2. Iron article lacking anemia, in the body iron deficiency because of develops.

3. Pernicious anemia (cyanocobalamin) lack of it depends.
4. Hemolytic anemia, erythrocytes from decay appear will be
5. Hypoplastic anemia, bone the bone function decreased when you leave develops.

Caused by blood loss anemia

This type of anemia is extremely common. Very different different in the specialty nurses that's it kind of anemia they observe Anemia take coming blood of leakage the most The most common causes are injury, abortion or childbirth, uterus raki or fibroma, stomach, intestines raki stomach or duodenal ulcer, cyst, pulmonary tuberculosis, or giving disintegration with passable another lungs diseases, viruses of hemorrhagic diathesis . After bleeding depending on the clinical picture and course of observed anemia him 2 type separate need:

1. Sharp blood loss as a result appear to be anemia
2. Chronic blood from loss appear to be anemia.

Sharp blood leaving blood a lot lost just in case to anemia take will come. Sharp blood from loss next anemia common to the signs impotence, ear rattle ,head rotation, unconscious leave enters. Man panting heart plays eye fades; the patient pale goes but from jaundice work too it won't happen ; the eye sclera hungry apostle color includes lips and another mucus curtains without blood being it seems Blood from flowing after pulse initially empty _ weak will be and speeding up goes The heart to hear at the points systolic noise is heard. Arterial pressure decreased goes Capillaries type colorless and rare will be This kind of in anemia turning around standing blood quantity in general less will be Sometimes turning around standing blood volume a little increased remains both because blood loss, usually of liquid from tissues to the blood fast pass with continue is enough. In this blood watered down — hydremic being remains. Heavy in events comatose condition starting with man hard panting the body temperature 34 -33° C up to decreased goes, heart tones barely is known muscles arguing cyanosis appear will be This heavy different of beards come output head the brain and heart like oxygen to the organs not enough stay with depends. Rapid, repeated (chronic) bleeding is rare even once even when blood is lost, sometimes leading to an exacerbation of anemia will come. However, for many years, it bleeds little by little in this way compensator changes as a result anemia signs-leads to non-occurrence of . How many times a year blood it varicose expansion of the rectal veins from bavasil blood leak example be takes Such patients initial in years blood since leaving after own in the situation change they do not notice, and their blood composition is normal for a long time will be But little by little, the new blood started disappearing as of help mother that's it hyperfunction begins to subside and with a state of hypofunction is exchanged. Blood the composition of erythrocytes and hemoglobin begins to decrease. Color index 0.6 —0.5 decreases to anemia, usually severe hypochromic character sweat have will be this iron lack of depends.

Iron from lack appear to be anemia

The amount of iron in the blood It drops to 3.6-5.4 $\mu\text{mol} /\text{l}$. This erythrocytes, leukocytes, thrombocytes decrease in the blood during the period the number does not change. About 80% of anemia is caused by iron deficiency. anemia caused by lack of Blood in it amount decreases in serum and bone marrow. Illness more common in women than in men . Iron

12 finger It is absorbed in the upper part of the intestine and small intestine absorption 2 stage passes:

1. Iron intestine through mucosal cells absorption.
2. Iron from cells to serum pass

Etiology and pathogenesis. To the origin of the disease one of the main reasons is blood loss. Little by little long time during blood when lost in the body iron quantity decreases. Food contained of iron physiological absorption is limited. Men get 18 mg of iron through food if he eats, 1-1.5 mg of it is absorbed. In women, mol done 12-15 mg of iron 1-1,5 _ mg is absorbed. If iron if more than 2 mg of iron is lost from the body per day signs of deficiency appear . Feel healthy 40 mg during menstruation in 10-25% of counting women more iron is lost. A lot of blood during menstruation Due to the loss, the iron requirement in women is 2.5-3 per daymg from more than will be But such in quantity iron in the intestinenot absorbed. So by doing one in the month 15-20 mg iron if it is not enough, iron deficiency in one year is 180-240 mg does. From this except each one pregnancy, giving birth and breastfeeding periods a woman 700-800 mg from less iron no does not harden . blood loss from the gastrointestinal tract during the development of bleeding also occupies a large place, this situation is more common in men. Although urinary blood loss does not cause anemia, anyway through the urine constantly losing erythrocytes iron will not lead to a shortage. Constant blood donor also in donors caused by iron deficiency anemia occurs. Sometimes congenital iron deficiency possible Premature chlorosis occurs in young girls and puberty to the period right will come. Stomach juice of the amount decline anemia can also occur as a result. It is gastrogenic anemia or Chlorohydrate anemia or late chlorosis is called

Clinical landscape. Clinical signs each different and different reasonsdepends will be Iron lack of signs suddenly is not known. The amount of hemoglobin in the blood decreased sharply. in ganda of tissues oxygen with enough lack of provision symptoms appear . Caused by iron deficiency with anemia, the patient has general weakness, rapid fatigue, headache turning around in the ears noise presence, the air lack of and complains of a fast heart beat. Sometimes the patient heart in the field pain feels The patient skin covers pale being sometimes it has a greenish tint (hence the word chlorosis). out). The patient checking when seen heart by tachycardia, heart peak in the field systolic noise note will be blood pressure decline possible EKG at T toothpick isoelectric on the line or Minus to be possible Unlike other types of anemia , iron deficiency- because it is not come came out in anemia sideropenia signs will be In this case, the patient's skin covers, nails and in her hair changes note will be done. Skin covers dry being _ leg and in the hands cracks appear will be 10-15% of patients have cracked mouth corners. In heavy types nails become thin and break easily. Koylonychia — spoon-shaped quote iron lack of it come came out is one of the symptoms of anemia. The patient's tongue is red pain possible (glossitis), language teats to atrophy meetingas a result, it becomes shiny and smooth. Iron deficiency Another symptom of anemia is muscle weakness. edema, nighttime incontinence in young girls. The patient is stiff when you laugh when coughing urine unable to hold remains. Iron reach because it is not gastrointestinal tract on the way too changes appear - gastric secretion is disturbed . With delayed chlorosis In sick patients, the sense of taste is disturbed. Go, let's cut there is a desire to eat things like coal . Kerosene the patient, acetone, naphthalene, from cars coming out of gases the smell likes the likes of

Conclusion is in order

Specific symptoms of diseases of the blood and blood-forming organs are identified when they are associated with diseases, that is, when the disease is examined in parts. Symptoms that can be detected in clinical examinations include the following:

Lethargy (or fatigue), rapid fatigue, panting, symptoms of anemia ("anemia" decreased amount of erythrocytes in the blood) or intoxication caused by rapid breakdown of leukocytes in hemoblastosis (acute and chronic) may be clinical signs. An increase in body temperature (fever) can be subtle or noticeable (in acute and chronic leukemia, the breakdown of leukocytes in a large amount). Purine molecules in the nucleus of leukocytes are released in large quantities, resulting in a pyrogenic effect. Fever can also occur in acute hemoblastosis and in the terminal stage of chronic hemoblastosis.

the skin is detected in several types of hemoblastosis (erythremia , lymphogranulomatosis) . Increased bleeding of several types , small rash-like burning of blood on the skin, hemorrhaging or bleeding are observed (from the nose, uterus, gastrointestinal tract, stomach, etc.). Most often, this condition is caused by a decrease in the amount of platelets in the blood and some oxygen substances involved in blood clotting, as well as a violation of the wall of small blood vessels.

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